

The Study of pH and Temperature Effect in Ramie Fibers Degumming Process Using Pectinase Enzyme

Luvya Nita^{1*}, Maya Komalasari², Atin Sumihartati³

¹ Politeknik STTT Bandung, luvyanita1@gmail.com

² Politeknik STTT Bandung, maya.komalasari@yahoo.com

³ Politeknik STTT Bandung, fh_atin@yahoo.co.id

* Correspondence: luvyanita1@gmail.com; Telp, : + 62-821-1984-2716

Abstract

Ramie fiber is a material derived from hemp bark. This fiber is still in a bundles form, because it is bound by a layer of gum. This adhesive must be removed because the ramie fiber needs to break down into strands of fibers before it can be spun into yarn. The degumming process aims to remove as many gum compounds as possible from the strands of ramie fibers. In crude ramie fibers, the gum content ranges from 25% -30%. After degumming process, the results of bleaching shows that the content of pectin found in ramie fibers decreases. Degumming process on ramie fibers uses pectinase enzyme that has the ability to hydrolyze pectin in ramie fibers content. The pectinase enzyme produced by microbes was chosen because of its advantages, such as low production cost, high production capacity, and, in a short time, easily affected productivity – by changing the pH and temperature. In order to determine the effect of pH and temperature on the physical properties of the fibers, the pH in the experiment ranged from 5, 6, 7 and 8, while the temperature ranged from 60 – 70 C. Based on the research that has been done, the pH and temperature have an effect on the results of the ramie fibers degumming process namely % weight reduction, tensile strength and whiteness index value. The optimum condition obtained was at pH 7 using a temperature of 70°C with % reduction in weight of 8.01%, tensile strength of 18.76 g/ tex and a whiteness index of 47.15%.

Keywords: ramie degumming, enzym pectinase, pH

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1. Introduction

The degumming process is the most crucial step in the processing of china grass (coarse ramie fibers). China grass is ramie fibers that has gone through a process of decortication which is the process of separating leaf stems from the bark. This process greatly determines the final quality of the fibers ready for spinning. China grass (coarse ramie fibers) contains gum ingredients between 25% to 30%. This gum consists mostly of pectin and hemicellulose. Since the hemp content of pectin is quite high, at 3% to 27%, the ramie fibers tend to be more rigid. In addition, the maximum gum residue content requirements in textile materials of ramie fibers are 1.5-2.5%. The processing of ramie fibers into china

grass is carried out using physical and chemical processes. The results are quite good, but this process has the disadvantage of producing waste, both solid, in the form of pieces of fibers which is a by product of decortization, and liquid waste, in the form of caustic soda which is harmful to the environment. To minimize the presence of waste in the processing of ramie into china grass, biological processing is an appropriate alternative because it does not produce waste.

Pectinase is an enzyme used in the degradation of pectin molecules, and are divided into three major groups, namely enzymes that deesterify (pektinaseterase), enzymes that carry out depolymerization (hydrolase and liase), and protopectinase. Deesterification enzymes cut the ester bond between the carboxyl group of the polyalgalactonic acid unit and the methyl group. Depolymerization enzymes divide the glycosidic a-14 bond on pectin compounds. Whereas protopectinase is a pectinase enzyme that dissolves protopectin^[1]. Enzymes have a certain pH for optimum activity. Changes in the pH of the solution affect the effectiveness of the active part of the enzyme in forming a substrate enzyme complex. Low or high pH can cause a denaturation process and result in a decrease in enzyme activity^[20]. The reaction using an enzyme catalyst is influenced by temperature. At low temperatures the reaction is slow while at higher temperatures the reaction is faster. The increase in temperature causes the denaturation process to occur, so the active part of the enzyme will be disrupted so that the concentration of the effectiveness of the enzyme decreases and the reaction speed decreases. The increase in temperature before the denaturation process can increase the reaction speed, but the increase in temperature at the start of the denaturation process will reduce the reaction speed. Since there are two opposite effects, an optimum point will occur, which is the right temperature for a reaction using the pectinase enzyme^[15,20].

Based on this, the purpose of this study was to determine the effect of pH and temperature of the pentinase enzyme on the ramie fibers degumming process, and to obtain the optimum value of pH and temperature of the pectinase enzyme in the degumming process of ramie fibers on the physical properties of fibers.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Ramie fibers (China grass) from Wonosobo, Enzym Pectinase (pectate lyase) 2% owf, Acetic acid (pH: 5,6,7), Sodium carbonate 10% (pH 8), Hydrogen peroxide 50%, Sodium hydroxide, Sodium silicate, wetting agent.

2.2. Method

Exhaust Ramie fibers (China grass) with HT dyeing machine laboratory scale with rasio 1: 10 , oven machine, 60 ° C and 70 ° C for 120 minutes. Testing Weight Reduction, Fibers Strength and Tensile Strength (SNI 08-1112-1989), Whitenessness Index for Fibers (SNI ISO 105-J02:2011), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM).

3. Results

3.1. Weight Reduction

The heavy-duty test is carried out after the ramie fibers degumming process, the test results are as follows:

Table 1. % Reduction in the weight of ramie fibers with variations in pH and temperature

Variation	Temperature	
	60°C	70°C
pH 5	6.64%	7.59%
pH 6	6.84%	8.01%
pH 7	7.09%	8.15%
pH 8	6.19%	7.54%

3.2. The Strength of Tensile and Stretch Fibers

Tensile strength and stretch of fibers carried out for ramie fibers after degumming and after bleaching process.

Table2. Tensile Strength of Ramie fibers after the degumming process(g/tex)

Variation	China Grass	Temperature	
		60°C	70°C
pH 5	31.16 g / tex	28.73 g / tex	24.77 g / tex
pH 6		27.11 g / tex	23.84 g / tex
pH 7		25.29 g / tex	22.44 g / tex
pH 8		28.97 g / tex	25.19 g / tex

Table 3. Tensile Fibers after the bleaching process (g/tex)

Variation	China Grass	Temperature	
		60°C	70°C
pH 5	31.16 g / tex	21.88 g / tex	20.16 g / tex
pH 6		20.95 g / tex	20.02 g / tex
pH 7		19.52 g / tex	18.76 g / tex
pH 8		21.59 g / tex	19.89 g / tex

3.3. Whiteness Index for Fibers

Whiteness-grade testing is done for fibers which are carried out by bleaching using hydrogen peroxide, the test results are as follows:

Table 4. Whiteness index of ramie fibers

Variation	Temperature	
	60°C	70°C
pH 5	22.24%	32.75%
pH 6	33.81%	34.51%
pH 7	46.75%	47.15%
pH 8	32.48%	36.40%

3.4. Scanning Electron Microscope(SEM)

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is used to observe the morphology of fibers in a longitudinal and transverse manner. SEM results are compared to ramie fibers which have not been carried out by the degumming process and after the degumming process. The degumming process is followed by a bleaching process which is carried out at optimum conditions for optimum pH and temperature.

Figure 1. (a) Cross section of fibers before the degumming process and (b) longitudinal cross section of fibers before the degumming process.

Figure 2. (a) Cross section of fibers after the degumming process and (b) longitudinal cross section of fibers after the degumming process.

4. Discussion

4.1 % Weight reduction

The graph of the relationship between the effect of temperature and pH on the degumming process using the pectinase enzyme on weight reduction can be seen in Figure 3 as follows:

Figure 3. Graph of the relationship between the influence of pH and temperature on the % reduction in the weight of ramie fibers.

The Figure 3 shows that the higher the temperature of the process is, the greater the weight reduction is, and the higher the pH of the solution is at or near neutral pH, the greater the weight reduction will be. It happens because when the temperature is 700 C, the activity of the enzyme rise that allows the molecules degrades more than in the temperature 600C, because enzyme activity decreases when the temperature is 600C. Increased temperature will increase molecular kinetic energy. Increased molecular kinetic energy also increases molecular motion so that the enzyme integrating pectin molecules also increases. Each enzyme has an optimal temperature, which is when the reaction rate is the fastest. The optimal increase in temperature in this study is 700C, when the temperature of the enzyme activity also increases because it allows the most degeneration of the pectin molecule.

Pectinase enzymes are sensitive to changes in pH and each enzyme has an optimum pH for its activity. It can be seen from Figure 3 that the effectiveness of the most active enzyme is in pH 7 conditions observed from the greatest weight reduction both at 600C and 700C. In the condition of pH 8 the weight reduction decreases because the change in pH (acid or base) will result in the denaturation process of the enzyme where the protein becomes inactive and does not work on the substrate. The pH which shows the highest enzyme activity of the enzyme is considered as the optimum pH. Most enzymes can work most effectively in the environment pH range and the optimum pH in this study is 7.

4.2 Testing the Strength of Tensile Ramie fibers

Figure 4. (a) The effect of pH and temperature after the degumming proceses, (b) the effect of pH and temperature after the bleaching process

In Figure 4, it can be seen that the higher the temperature of the ramie fibers degumming process, the more the tensile strength decreases and the higher the pH or close to the neutral pH, the tensile strength also decreases. However, when the pH (acid or base) changes, the tensile strength increases compared to pH 7. It happens because in the pH (acid or base) condition, the enzyme protein becomes inactive and does not work on the substrate, so there is still a lot of gum in the fibers which makes the fibers unravel between one another, and the value of strength continues to rise.

The results of the tensile strength of ramie fibers after the bleaching process can be seen in Figure 4. The result shows that the higher the temperature of the ramie fibers degumming process, the tensile strength decreases and the higher the pH or close to neutral pH, the tensile strength decreases. Oxidizers such as H₂O₂ are strong oxidizers which can cause damage to ramie fibers. The damage to this fibers will result in a decrease in the tensile strength of the fibers and a decrease in the tensile strength depends on how much damage the fibers has. This occurs because the free oxygen released by H₂O₂ is more reactive and more unstable, so when it is done in an atmosphere of alkaline, hydrogen bonds with the OH primary between two molecular chains of fibers in the presence of NaOH and will be separated into OH free primary. Moreover, the compactness of fibers when carried out withdrawal as a result the tensile strength becomes less. The lowest tensile strength is at conditions of 700C and pH 7. This is because the gum has disappeared so hydrogen peroxide will damage and break the cellulose chain resulting in the decrease of the value of the strength.

4.3 Whiteness Index for Fibers

Fibers derived from natural fibers tend to have a slightly brownish yellow color, as do ramie fibers. Whiteness of ramie fibers is a parameter that must be met, because the whiteness index is one of the important parameters that affect the quality of ramie fibers. The bleaching process aims to whiten ramie fibers by removing the components of the absorbing natural pigments in the fibers, especially the lignin functional group. The process of cooking with pectinase enzymes can only remove impurities in the fibers but cannot whiten the fibers, so the fibers is bleached. The process of bleaching ramie fibers uses H₂O₂ 50%. The highest whiteness index value is at conditions of 70°C and pH 7. The

effect of the degumming process using the enzyme pectinase on the whiteness index of ramie fibers can be seen in Figure 5 as follows:

Figure 5.Graph the effect of the degumming process on the whiteness index of ramie fibers.

In Figure 5 it can be seen that the higher the temperature of the ramie fibers degumming process , the greater the value of the whiteness index and the higher the pH or close to the neutral pH, the greater the value of the whiteness index. Because the greater the weight reduction, the more dirt or gum dissolves, so that it will facilitate the bleaching process using hydrogen peroxide in an alkaline atmosphere that will produce active oxygen which oxidizes the existing natural pigments so that the material becomes whitened. The hydrogen peroxide decomposition chemical reaction can be seen in chemical reactions as follows:

From the above reaction, hydrogen peroxide will break down into HO₂⁻ in an alkaline atmosphere, oxygen is then formed which will oxidize the double bond of natural pigment into a single, non-colored bond so that the material becomes whitened. The bleaching process is carried out in alkaline conditions with the addition of sodium hydroxide, so if the previous cooking process is not perfect, it is refined. Moreover, the removal of impurities becomes cleaner and the ingredients become whiter because of the oxidation process of natural pigments. When compared with all variations, it turns out that the whitening process with the highest whiteness grade value is degrading ramie fibers with a temperature of 70°C and pH 7, this is because that process of gum removal is more effective.

4.4 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

Decortified ramie fibers is a hemp tree that is processed using a decortication machine to obtain stem fibers. The degumming process reduces gum as a pretreatment before proceeding to the next process. In ramie fibers from decortication and degumming, there are physical differences. Degummed fibers are softer and thinner than decorticated ramie fibers. The results of the decortication process have brown fibers, but the fibers degummed are faded brown. That shows that gum has been removed.

Figures 1 and 2 show the surface of ramie fibers before the degumming (China grass) process and after the degumming process with a temperature of 70°C and pH 7. The Figure is the SEM micro-photograph, and the fibers surface morphology was observed by SEM at 500 X and 1000 X for cross section. The results of SEM photo observations are clear so that they can be analyzed. The results of the observation show that the treatment of the degumming process affects the quality of the fibers surface. Fibers without treatment shows that the structures of fibrils in ramie fibers are still covered by gum and are still in bundles form. In the treatment of degumming process with a temperature of 70°C and pH 7 the surface of the fibers becomes clean and smooth. Fibers can decompose easily into a single fibers due to the reduced gum and pectin content between fibers shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Longitudinal surface (a) Ramie fibers before the *degumming* process(China grass). (b) After the degumming process with a temperature of 70°C and pH 7

5. Conclusion

- Higher pH and temperature affect the % weight reduction, the tensile strength g / tex and the whiteness index value.
- The optimum condition obtained was at pH 7 using a temperature of 70°C with % reduction in weight of 8.01%, tensile strength of 18,76 g/tex and a whiteness index of 47.15%. The degumming process of ramie fibers using the enzyme pectinase can affect the whiteness grade value of ramie fibers.

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